

Iterative hydraulic interval state estimation for water distribution networks

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ABSTRACT

State estimation of hydraulics (i.e. pressure and flows) in water distribution networks is an important tool for efficient and resilient operation. However, hydraulic state estimation is a challenging task in practice due to the scarcity of measurements and the presence of several modeling uncertainties. Standard state estimation techniques may produce unreliable estimates with no information of the estimation error magnitude, especially when historical data are used in place of missing measurements. In this paper, we propose a comprehensive

24 methodology for generating hydraulic state bounding estimates by considering both mea-
25 surement and parametric uncertainties. The methodology is based on solving the nonlinear
26 interval hydraulic equations using bounding linearization, a technique that restricts the non-
27 linearities within a convex set, thus converting the problem in a form which is solvable using
28 linear optimization. An iterative procedure improves the bounding linearization, converging
29 to the tightest possible bounds. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed method-
30 ology produces tight state bounds that can replace Monte-Carlo simulations.

31 **Keywords:** interval, bounds, optimization, state estimation, water distribution networks

32 INTRODUCTION

33 The water industry is being modernized with the installation of sensors for monitoring
34 Water Distribution Networks (WDN) and computer systems to process these data. Inte-
35 grated platforms are already being developed that algorithmically combine real-time sensor
36 measurements from Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems, geographic
37 information systems (GIS), and hydraulic models to provide useful information to the op-
38 erators. A state estimation algorithm infers the complete system state, such as water flows
39 in pipes, consumer water demands, pressures at nodes and tank levels, using the available
40 measurement set and network equations. A complete view of the network state supports
41 the decision-making process and enables the efficient operation of these systems, improves
42 customer service and enables the early detection of emergency events, thus minimizing their
43 impact. Examples of the use of state estimation in real systems include the use for online
44 burst detection (Okeya et al. 2014) as well as for online modelling (Machell et al. 2010) and
45 control of WDN (Rao and Salomons 2007).

46 Standard state estimation techniques require a measurement set that makes the system
47 observable, i.e. the sensor number and locale ensure that the system state can be calculated
48 (Bargiela 1985; Nagar and Powell 2000; Díaz et al. 2016). Additionally, the statistical
49 characterization of sensor measurement error is needed to give more weight to measurements
50 originating from more accurate sensors. Then, using a mathematical model of the network, a

51 state estimation algorithm can infer the system state. Many approaches have been proposed
52 to solve the state estimation problem for water systems, such as Kalman Filtering and
53 Weighted Least Squares (WLS), with the latter being the most widely used and varied. The
54 above methods produce a point in state-space and are referred to as *point state estimation*
55 (Powell et al. 1988; Andersen et al. 2001; Kang and Lansey 2009).

56 State estimation in WDN is a challenging task, mainly due to the scarcity of measure-
57 ments. In contrast to other large scale engineering systems (e.g. power systems) where the
58 number of measurements guarantees observability, in WDN observability is almost never
59 achievable with the available measurements. Some parts of the WDN may be widely moni-
60 tored, such as the transport network, however even a single sensor failure could make these
61 parts unobservable (Vrachimis et al. 2016). The large area covered by WDN and the large
62 number of system states is one of the main reasons that an impractical number of sensors
63 must be installed to guarantee observability. A common practice to reduce the complexity,
64 is to skeletonize the network by treating a group of consumers as a single demand point. It
65 is then possible to use *pseudo-measurements*, which are demand estimates determined from
66 population densities and historical data, to complement the missing measurements (Hutton
67 et al. 2014). Recent advances in water demands research have also made possible the higher
68 resolution modeling of water demands, thus reducing the need for skeletonization of networks
69 and increasing the accuracy of state estimation (Avni et al. 2015).

70 The use of pseudo-measurements may introduce new problems to the state estimation
71 process, as they are highly uncertain and the resulting estimates may deviate significantly
72 from the real system state. This in turn could affect other algorithms which rely on state-
73 estimation, such as feedback control or fault-diagnosis. Efforts have been made to charac-
74 terize the uncertainty of pseudo-measurements (Bargiela and Hainsworth 1989), but it is
75 improbable that a statistical characterization will be available. Thus, standard state es-
76 timation techniques such as WLS may not be capable of producing a reliable measure of
77 the estimation error. Consequently, researchers have tried to combine online estimation of

78 demands with state estimation, in order for the latter to be more accurate (Preis et al. 2011).

79 Another significant source of uncertainty which complicates WDN state estimation is
80 modelling and parameter uncertainty. Recent works provide explicit expressions for the
81 sensitivity of the state estimation problem to these uncertainties (Díaz et al. 2018). Typically,
82 the network topology is assumed known, especially after the process of skeletonization which
83 simplifies the network graph. However, even when the topology is known, pipe parameters
84 such as length and diameter are rarely known accurately and estimates are used in place.
85 This is especially true for pipe roughness coefficients, which along with length and diameter,
86 are used to calculate the headloss across pipes. This is why, even with an observable sensor
87 configuration, model calibration is required *a priori* or during state estimation for the latter
88 to produce feasible solutions (Gao 2017). Model calibration can be considered as the inverse
89 problem of state estimation, during which estimates of the unknown model parameters are
90 calculated based on measurements (Kapelan et al. 2003; Savic et al. 2009). But even after
91 calibration, it is possible that the calculated parameter set satisfies the constraints imposed
92 by measurements, but deviates from the true parameter set.

93 Considering the many unknowns and uncertainties in WDN state-estimation, it is evident
94 that accurate state-estimates are difficult to be generated without some kind of trade-off. A
95 practical approach for state estimation in the presence of demand and modeling uncertainty,
96 is *interval state estimation* (Bargiela et al. 2003; Langowski and Brdys 2007). This approach
97 models the uncertainties on input data as intervals, defined by lower and upper bounds.
98 Then, considering this bounded uncertainty, interval state estimation provides lower and
99 upper bounds on the state estimates, in contrast to point state estimation methods which
100 only provide a single point. Providing a range of values for each state, is often more useful
101 to an operator than providing point estimates which give no indication on their proximity
102 to the true state value. Additionally, having reliable interval state estimation is essential in
103 many methodologies related to event and fault detection such as leakage detection (Pérez
104 et al. 2009), water contamination detection (Eliades et al. 2015) and sensor fault detection

105 (Vrachimis et al. 2015).

106 The use of bounds for the representation of measurement uncertainty and the subsequent
107 calculation of state estimate bounds was introduced in (Bargiela and Hainsworth 1989). This
108 idea was further developed in (Brdys and Chen 1994) as the *set-bounded* state estimation
109 problem. The process of calculating bounds for state estimates caused by measurement un-
110 certainty is also referred to as Confidence Limit Analysis which can be solved using different
111 approaches, including Neural Networks (Gabrys and Bargiela 1997), the Error Maximization
112 method (Arsene et al. 2011), the Ellipsoid method and Linear Programming (Bargiela et al.
113 2003). All these approaches assume a known network model which can be linearized in order
114 to solve the non-linear equations that characterize WDN and provide state bounds based
115 on measurement uncertainty. Few methodologies can guarantee the inclusion of the true
116 state in the bounds based on given uncertainty, while the effect of modeling uncertainty is
117 not considered. Another approach that could incorporate modeling uncertainty is the use
118 of Monte-Carlo Simulations (MCS), where state bound estimates are obtained by randomly
119 generating and evaluating a large number of model parameter sets or realizations (Pasha
120 and Lansey 2010). This approach requires a sufficiently large number of simulations, and
121 even then some cases may not be covered, leading to underestimation of the range of the
122 true state bounds.

123 In this work we propose a new interval hydraulic state-estimation approach for WDN that
124 considers the combined effect of bounded measurement and modeling uncertainties. The
125 proposed methodology calculates the bounds on state estimates using the nonlinear form
126 of the network equations, by also modeling pressure-dependent demands and background
127 leakages. The nonlinear modeling guarantees that when accurate uncertainty bounds are
128 provided, the bounds on state estimates will include the true system state. This is achieved
129 using bounding linearization, a technique which restricts the nonlinearities within a convex
130 set, thus converting the hydraulic equations in a form where the minimum and maximum of
131 each state can be found using linear optimization. Then, an iterative procedure is followed

132 to minimize the distance between upper and lower state bounds, by improving the bounding
133 linearization at each step and converging to the tightest possible bounds. The contributions
134 of this work are:

- 135 • The consideration of both modeling uncertainty, in the form of uncertain parameters,
136 as well as measurement uncertainty in the interval state estimation problem for WDN.
- 137 • The development of a novel algorithm that calculates tight hydraulic bounding esti-
138 mates based on the considered uncertainties.
- 139 • The use of the nonlinear form of the hydraulic equations which also considers pressure-
140 dependent demands and background leakages, in order to ensure that the bounding
141 estimates guarantee the inclusion of the true system state if the uncertainties have
142 been accurately represented.

143 This paper is organized as follows: Section “Problem formulation” formulates the prob-
144 lem of hydraulic state estimation in WDN where the uncertainty on model parameters and
145 measurements is represented by intervals. Section “Iterative Hydraulic Interval State Es-
146 timation” presents a methodology to solve this problem based on the Iterative Hydraulic
147 Interval State Estimation (IHISE) algorithm. In Section “Case Studies” this methodology
148 is applied on different benchmark water networks and its performance is assessed.

149 **PROBLEM FORMULATION**

150 The topology of a WDN is modeled by a directed graph denoted as $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{L})$. Let
151 $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n_n\}$ be the set of all nodes, where $|\mathcal{N}| = n_n$ is the total number of nodes. These
152 represent junctions of pipes, consumer water demand locations, reservoirs and tanks. The
153 unknown quantity associated with nodes is the *hydraulic head*, indicated by h_i . Reservoirs
154 and water tanks that have level sensors installed, can be considered as nodes with known
155 head. We define the set of nodes with unknown head $\mathcal{N}_u = \{1, \dots, n_u\}$, where $|\mathcal{N}_u| = n_u$
156 is the number of nodes with unknown head. The set of nodes with known head is defined
157 as $\mathcal{N}_h = \{n_u + 1, \dots, n_n\}$, where $|\mathcal{N}_h| = n_h$ is the number of nodes with known head and

158 $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}_u \cup \mathcal{N}_h$. Each node j with unknown head is associated with a water consumer demand
 159 at the node location, denoted by $q_{ext,j}$.

160 Let $\mathcal{L} = \{1, \dots, n_l\}$ be the set of links, where $|\mathcal{L}| = n_l$ is the total number of links.
 161 These represent network pipes, water pumps and pipe valves, with the last two being the
 162 main hydraulic control elements in a water network. We define the set of links that represent
 163 pipes as $\mathcal{L}_p = \{1, \dots, n_p\}$, where $|\mathcal{L}_p| = n_p$ is the total number of pipes. We also define
 164 the set of links that represent pumps as $\mathcal{L}_{pu} = \{n_p + 1, \dots, n_l\}$, where $|\mathcal{L}_{pu}| = n_{pu}$ is the
 165 total number of pumps. The unknown quantity associated with a link i is the *water flow*,
 166 indicated by q_i .

167 **Formulation of hydraulic equations**

168 It is a common practice in WDN to receive sensor measurements of flows, pressures or
 169 tank water levels at constant time intervals, which typically range from five minutes to one
 170 hour. These sensors may also give an average measurement for the elapsed time interval, thus
 171 fast changing dynamics (e.g. pressure transients) are neglected. As a result, standard state
 172 estimation in WDN is carried out at steady state, with the system state being recalculated
 173 when measurements arrive.

174 In this work we assume that only lower and upper bounds on measurements are available.
 175 The bounds can be derived from real sensor measurements, or from population densities and
 176 historical data (pseudo-measurements). The measurement bounds are available at every
 177 discrete time step k for all nodal demand outflows and for all tank and reservoir levels.
 178 This sensor configuration guarantees the topological observability of the network. Other
 179 sensor configurations are also possible, given that they satisfy the topological observability
 180 condition, which can be checked using the algorithm in (Díaz et al. 2017). The vector of
 181 measured external water demand outflow is indicated by $\bar{q}_{ext}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$. The known head
 182 vector, which results from tank and reservoir level measurements, is indicated by $\bar{h}_{ext}(k) \in$
 183 \mathbb{R}^{n_l} . The unknown state of the network are the water flows in pipes $\bar{q}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ and the
 184 unknown hydraulic heads at nodes $\bar{h}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$.

185 The state is calculated using a hydraulic model of a WDN, which is a set of equations
186 derived from the laws of: 1) conservation of energy and 2) conservation of mass in the
187 network. In this work we use the *pipe formulation* of these equations as used by (Todini and
188 Pilati 1987), which has been shown to be robust in computer simulations (Rossman 2000).
189 The only dynamic component of these equations are the changing tank levels (Boulos et al.
190 2006). Because tank levels are assumed to be measured, the resulting hydraulic equations
191 are not dynamic, thus the discrete time notation k is omitted. The formulation of these
192 equations follows.

193 *Conservation of energy equations*

194 Energy in WDN is associated with the head at nodes and when water flows through a
195 network link i which connects two nodes, a flow dependent head function $f_i(q_i)$ describes
196 the change in head. In the case of pipes, energy is dissipated due to friction of water flowing
197 through the pipe, resulting in head-loss between two connected nodes. Head-loss depends
198 on the water flow through the pipe but also on pipe parameters. Each pipe $i \in \mathcal{L}_p$ is
199 characterized by pipe length l_i , pipe diameter d_i and pipe roughness coefficient c_i . All these
200 quantities are used in the empirical Hazen-Williams (H-W) formula (Boulos et al. 2006) to
201 calculate head-loss. The effect of pipe parameters in this formula is aggregated in the H-W
202 resistance coefficient r_i of each pipe, which is a function $f_{HW}^r : \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}^+ \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$ of
203 pipe parameters, defined as: $r_i = f_{HW}^r(c_i, d_i, l_i)$. The head-loss across pipe $i \in \mathcal{L}_p$ is then
204 calculated using the H-W formula as follows:

$$205 \quad f_i(q_i) = r_i |q_i|^{(\nu-1)} q_i, \quad (1)$$

206 where ν is a constant exponent associated with the H-W formula and q_i is the water flow in
207 pipe i .

208 Another example of network element are pumps $i \in \mathcal{L}_{pu}$ which are characterized by a
209 head-flow curve, which is used to relate the flow through the pump to the head-gain across

210 the pump, according to each pump specifications. This is given by:

$$211 \quad f_i(q_i) = -(w_1 - w_2 q_i^{w_3}), \quad (2)$$

212 where $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathbb{R}$ are coefficients of the pump head-flow curve, while the minus sign
 213 indicates that in the case of pumps there is head-gain instead of head-loss.

214 The energy equations for all the network links, considering elements modeled by (1) and
 215 (2), can be written as follows:

$$216 \quad f_i(q_i) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_u} (B_{ij} h_j) = h_{ext,i}, \quad i \in \mathcal{L}, \quad (3)$$

217 where:

- 218 • h_j is the unknown head of node $j \in \mathcal{N}_u$.
- 219 • $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times n_u}$ is the incidence flow matrix, indicating the connectivity of nodes with
 220 links. Element $B_{ij} = +1$ if the direction of link i enters node j ; element $B_{ij} = -1$ if
 221 the direction of link i leaves from node j ; otherwise $B_{ij} = 0$. Nodes with known head
 222 are excluded from this matrix.
- 223 • $h_{ext,i}$ is the sum of known (measured) heads that appear in each equation $i \in \mathcal{L}$. In
 224 vector notation, the known head vector is given by $\bar{h}_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$.

225 *Conservation of mass equations*

226 The conservation of mass law for a node $j \in \mathcal{N}_u$ is similar to Kirchhoff's current law in
 227 electric circuit analysis and can be summarized as follows: the sum of branch water flows
 228 from pipes incident to a node j must be equal to the node's external water demand $q_{ext,j}$.

229 A demand-driven modeling approach assumes that the demand at each node is indepen-
 230 dent of the pressure at that node. However, this analysis is not valid when power outages, fire
 231 fighting, pipe breaks or temporarily closed portions of a WDN lead to pressure-deficit condi-
 232 tions. In those cases, the consumers do not receive the requested demand, thus the modeling

233 of demand is no longer valid and a pressure-dependent demand modeling is recommended.
 234 The pressure-demand relationship can be modeled by multiplying the user requested demand
 235 $q_{ext,j}$ at node j by the pressure depended function $f_{ext,j}(h_j)$, which is given by (Wagner et al.
 236 1988; Giustolisi and Laucelli 2011; Klise et al. 2017):

$$237 \quad f_{ext,j}(h_j) = \begin{cases} 0 & h_j \leq H_{min,j} \\ \left(\frac{h_j - H_{min,j}}{H_{req,j} - H_{min,j}} \right)^{0.5} & H_{min,j} \leq h_j \leq H_{req,j} \\ 1 & h_j \geq H_{req,j} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

238 In (4), $H_{req,j}$ is the head above which the consumer can receive the requested demand $q_{ext,j}$
 239 (depends on node elevation), $H_{min,j}$ is the minimum desired head at node j (depends on
 240 node elevation) below which the consumer does not receive any water.

241 Background leakage flows are also present in real WDN and are modeled as an added
 242 demand component at nodes. Leakage flows are pressure-dependent and are modeled similarly
 243 to pressure-driven demands as follows (Giustolisi et al. 2008):

$$244 \quad q_{leak,j}(h_j) = \begin{cases} \beta_j (h_j - Z_j)^{\gamma_j}, & h_j - Z_j > 0 \\ 0 & h_j - Z_j \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

245 where Z_j is the elevation of node j , and β_j and γ_j are leakage parameters depending on pipe
 246 deterioration and material.

247 The conservation of mass equations, considering all the nodes of the network, can be
 248 written using the incidence flow matrix as follows:

$$249 \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} (B_{ij}^\top q_i) = q_{ext,j} f_{ext,j}(h_j) + q_{leak,j}(h_j), \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u. \quad (6)$$

250 In vector notation, the requested external water demands for all nodes are given by $\bar{q}_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$
 251 and the leakage flow at nodes by $\bar{q}_{leak} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$. Equations (3) and (6) define the network state,
 252 which are the water flows in pipes and hydraulic heads at nodes, indicated by $\bar{x} = [\bar{q}^\top \bar{h}^\top]^\top$.

Measurement and parameter uncertainty

As mentioned in the “Introduction” section, we consider sensor measurements, or pseudo-measurements that are uncertain, with a bounded measurement error. We assume that these are available for all nodal demand outflows, as well as for all tank and reservoir levels, guaranteeing an observable sensor configuration. The network topology is available in the hydraulic model, but pipe parameters are only approximately known.

The uncertainties are modeled in this work using intervals, which is equivalent to a uniform probability distribution. For notational convenience, we adopt the convention of denoting intervals in bold. Let $\bar{\mathbf{v}} = [\bar{v}^l, \bar{v}^u]$ be a closed interval vector, where \bar{v}^l is the lower bound vector and \bar{v}^u is the upper bound vector, such that: $\bar{\mathbf{v}} = \{\bar{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n : v_i^l \leq v_i \leq v_i^u, \forall i = \{1, \dots, n\}\}$, and n is the size of the vector. Note that calculations performed in equations containing intervals require the use of interval arithmetic (Daumas et al. 2009; Kearfott 1996; Moore et al. 2009).

The uncertain requested water demands and the reservoir/tank levels are given by the interval vectors $\bar{\mathbf{q}}_{ext} = [\bar{q}_{ext}^l, \bar{q}_{ext}^u]$ and $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{ext} = [\bar{h}_{ext}^l, \bar{h}_{ext}^u]$ respectively. Note that, measurement bounds that are derived from nodes with actual sensors, do not require to be accompanied by a pressure-dependent function, so $f_{ext,j}(h_j) = 1$.

We also consider the uncertainty on the head function $f_i(q_i)$. When this function contains uncertain parameters, these will be modelled as intervals defined by a lower and upper bound, and the head function will be indicated in bold as $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$. Uncertainty in pipe parameters is included in the uncertain H-W coefficients r_i . These are calculated using uncertain pipe parameters, which are the roughness coefficients c_i , diameter d_i and length l_i . For a certain pipe i , the uncertain H-W coefficient is given by: $\mathbf{r}_i = [r_i^l, r_i^u]$. An interval H-W coefficient transforms the pipe headloss function given by (1), into an interval function given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_i(q_i) = \mathbf{r}_i |q_i|^{\nu-1} q_i, \quad i \in \mathcal{L}_p \quad (7)$$

278 Similarly, for i corresponding to a pump with an uncertain pump curve, (2) becomes:

$$279 \quad \mathbf{f}_i(q_i) = -(\mathbf{w}_1 - \mathbf{w}_2 q_i^{\mathbf{w}_3}), \quad i \in \mathcal{L}_{pu}. \quad (8)$$

280 The uncertainty is considered in the case of leakage modeling, is on the leakage param-
 281 eters, which can be represented by the intervals $\beta_j = [\beta_j^l, \beta_j^u]$ and $\gamma_j = [\gamma_j^l, \gamma_j^u]$. This will
 282 result in an interval leakage function $\mathbf{q}_{leak,j}(h_j)$.

283 As a practical note, a calibration pre-step of network topology parameters is recom-
 284 mended, as it will reduce the uncertainty of these parameters in the sense that their bound-
 285 aries will be more restrictive. As a result, the bounded state estimates calculated by the
 286 IHISE algorithm will be less conservative. In this work the parameter boundaries are as-
 287 sumed constant for all time steps, because these parameters vary very slowly over time. The
 288 parameters can be updated whenever a calibration procedure takes place for the network.

289 **Problem definition**

290 The problem of solving the hydraulic equations of a WDN when these contain uncertainty
 291 in the form of intervals, is reduced to finding the set of all point solutions for the state
 292 $\bar{x} = [\bar{q}^\top \bar{h}^\top]^\top$, that satisfy the following systems of equations:

$$293 \quad \mathbf{f}_i(q_i) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_u} (B_{ij} h_j) = \mathbf{h}_{ext,i}, \quad i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (9a)$$

$$294 \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} (B_{ij}^\top q_i) = \mathbf{q}_{ext,j} f_{ext,j}(h_j) + \mathbf{q}_{leak,j}(h_j), \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u \quad (9b)$$

296 Problem (9) is a Nonlinear Interval System of Equations (NISE) and the set of solutions
 297 for \bar{x} that satisfy (9) may have a rather complex form that needs to be described with non-
 298 linear functions. This is why, in the literature, ‘interval solutions’ are most often considered,
 299 with the aim of finding the Interval Hull (IH) solution, i.e. the smallest interval vector \bar{x}
 300 containing all solutions for the NISE. Finding the IH solution to general NISE is a very
 301 challenging problem; even for the general Linear Interval System of Equations (LISE), find-

302 ing the IH is an NP-hard problem. For this reason there are several solutions proposed in
303 the literature that approximate the IH, either with an Outer Interval (OI) solution, which
304 is any interval vector enclosing the IH solution, or with an INner Interval (INI) solution,
305 which is any interval vector that is a subset of the IH solution. Most approaches deal with
306 the problem of finding an OI solution, while the INI solution is used as a measure of the
307 overestimation of the solution (Neumaier and Pownuk 2007; Kolev 2004a). An example of a
308 method for finding the INI solution to a NISE are Monte-Carlo Simulations, where solutions
309 are calculated by randomly generating and evaluating a large number of non-interval equa-
310 tions with parameters within the defined intervals (Eliades et al. 2015). The set of solutions
311 is always a subset of the IH solution.

312 The literature on finding an OI solution to NISE is limited, but some approaches have
313 been proposed, such as (Kolev 2004b), which uses affine arithmetic to represent the equations
314 and interval linearization to deal with the nonlinearities. However, this approach does not
315 consider interval multiplicative terms in the nonlinear functions, thus cannot be applied to
316 (9). The solution to NISE can also be approached using optimization, as in (Jiang et al. 2008)
317 where the task of solving nonlinear interval number programming problems was investigated.
318 This method, however, does not ensure that the solution is an OI, thus it is not suitable for
319 use with methodologies such as fault detection which require outer bounds on states.

320 Good approaches in the literature that provide tight OI solutions exist for Linear Interval
321 Systems of Equations (LISE) and are mainly divided in two categories. The first uses interval
322 arithmetic (Daumas et al. 2009; Moore et al. 2009) to find the solution. Due to the fact
323 that when using interval arithmetic to solve LISE, the solution interval is inherently an
324 overestimation, iterative methods are used to approximate the IH solution, such as the Gauss
325 Elimination method, LU decomposition method and the iterative Jacobi method (Zieniuk
326 et al. 2015). The second category formulates LISE as an Interval Linear Programming
327 problem, where intervals can exist both in the objective function and in the constraints
328 (Chinneck and Ramadan 2000; Huang and Cao 2011). This approach is promising since

329 the formulation of the equations as a Linear Program provides the opportunity to add and
330 manipulate constraints to the problem. Additionally, powerful software that solve Linear
331 Programs efficiently exist, which reduce computation time.

332 **ITERATIVE HYDRAULIC INTERVAL STATE ESTIMATION**

333 In this work we propose an iterative method for finding an OI solution of the NISE in (9),
334 named *Iterative Hydraulic Interval State Estimation* (IHISE), which closely approximates the
335 IH solution. This method deals with the nonlinearities in (9) using bounding linearization,
336 which encloses the interval nonlinearities in a convex set and converts (9) into a system
337 of linear inequalities. The resulting linear inequalities are then appropriately formulated
338 into a Linear Program and new bounds on the state variables are calculated. An iterative
339 procedure then approximates the IH solution of (9) by using the new bounds on the states
340 to improve the bounding linearization. Initial bounds on state variables can be defined from
341 physical properties of WDN.

342 The IHISE algorithm is comprised of five main steps:

- 343 1. Find initial bounds on the state variables using physical constraints of the system.
- 344 2. Use bounding linearization to bound the nonlinearities in a convex set.
- 345 3. Formulate Linear Programs (LPs) for each state using the resulting linear inequalities.
- 346 4. Solve one maximization and one minimization LP for each state to produce new upper
347 and lower bounds.
- 348 5. Iteratively improve the OI solution of (9) by repeating steps 2 to 4 until convergence
349 of bounds.

350 Next, the five steps of IHISE are described in detail.

351 **Step 1: Initial bounds on state vector**

352 The first step of the IHISE algorithm is to impose initial bounds on the state vector
353 $\bar{x} = [\bar{q}^\top \bar{h}^\top]^\top$ which should be an OI solution of (9). The initial bounds on the unknown head
354 vector \bar{h} are given by the interval vector $\bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(0)} = [\bar{h}^l{}^{(0)}, \bar{h}^u{}^{(0)}]$ and are chosen by considering

355 physical properties of the network. The minimum head vector $\bar{h}^l(0)$ is set equal to the
 356 elevation of each node and the maximum head vector $\bar{h}^u(0)$ is set equal to the sum of reservoir
 357 and pump heads, which is the maximum head that any node in the network can have.

358 The special structure (9a), in which each equation contains only one flow state q_i , allows
 359 us to use the initial bounds on heads $\mathbf{h}^{(0)}$ to find the initial bounds on the flows. We rewrite
 360 (9a) as follows:

$$361 \quad \mathbf{f}_i(q_i) = - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_u} (B_{ij} \mathbf{h}_j^{(0)}) + \mathbf{h}_{ext,i} = \mathbf{y}_i, \quad (10)$$

362 where $\mathbf{y}_i = [y_i^l, y_i^u]$ is a known interval derived from the known terms in (10) using interval
 363 analysis. The function $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$, when $i \in \mathcal{L}_p$, is given by (7). This function is *inclusion*
 364 *isotonic* (Moore et al. 2009) meaning that if $\mathbf{q}_i^1 \subseteq \mathbf{q}_i^2$ then $\mathbf{f}(q_i^1) \subseteq \mathbf{f}(q_i^2)$. This property
 365 enables the derivation of analytical bounds on the unknown pipe flows, by rearranging (10)
 366 with respect to q_i , $i \in \mathcal{L}_p$.

367 In the case of pumps, $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$ is given by (8). This function is not inclusion isotonic in
 368 its whole range, but this property holds in the special case when $q_i > 0$ or $q_i < 0$. This
 369 implies that the flow direction in pump links needs to be known *a priori*, which is a valid
 370 assumption, since pumps are physically restricted to move water in one direction. Assuming
 371 that the flow in pump links is always positive, the bounds on flows q_i , $i \in \mathcal{L}_{pu}$ can be found
 372 by rearranging (10) with respect to q_i .

373 The initial bounds on the flow state vector are denoted by $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)} = [\bar{q}^l(0), \bar{q}^u(0)]$. An
 374 analytical derivation of these bounds for pipes and pumps is given in Appendix S1 of the
 375 Supplemental Data.

376 **Step 2: Bounding linearization of interval nonlinear terms**

377 This step aims at enclosing in a convex set \mathcal{S} the nonlinear uncertain functions that
 378 exist in Problem (9). This will allow the formulation of a Linear Program. Problem (9)
 379 contains three nonlinear uncertain functions: $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$, $\mathbf{q}_{ext,j} f_{ext,j}(h_j)$ and $\mathbf{q}_{leak,j}(h_j)$, which are
 380 all functions of one bounded variable. The bounds on these variables have been calculated

381 in Step 1, such that for flow variables $q_i \in [q_i^l, q_i^u]$ and for head variables $h_j \in [h_j^l, h_j^u]$. The
 382 goal is to construct convex sets \mathcal{S} that include all the points of the uncertain functions in
 383 the given range, e.g. $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i) \in \mathcal{S}, \forall q_i \in [q_i^l, q_i^u], i \in \mathcal{L}$.

384 In this work we design the convex sets \mathcal{S} using bounding linearization (Kolev 2004b).
 385 This procedure can be used on any uncertain nonlinear function of one bounded variable
 386 and it encloses the function between two lines. For example, given the nonlinear uncertain
 387 function $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$ for an interval $q_i \in [q_i^l, q_i^u]$, a lower line $f_{L,i}^l(q_i) = \lambda_i^l q_i + \beta_i^l$ and an upper line
 388 $f_{L,i}^u(q_i) = \lambda_i^u q_i + \beta_i^u$ can be designed such that:

$$389 \quad f_{L,i}^l(q_i) \leq \mathbf{f}_i(q_i) \leq f_{L,i}^u(q_i), \forall q_i \in [q_i^l, q_i^u], i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (11)$$

390 The goal of the bounding linearization procedure is to define the line parameters to minimize
 391 the area of the resulting convex set \mathcal{S} . A detailed description on how to obtain linearization
 392 bounds for each of the nonlinear functions considered can be found in Appendix S2 of the
 393 Supplemental Data.

394 **Step 3: Formulation of Linear Program**

395 The bounding linearization of Step 2, yields linear inequality constraints for the interval
 396 functions $\mathbf{f}_i(q_i)$, $\mathbf{q}_{ext,j} f_{ext,j}(h_j)$ and $\mathbf{q}_{leak,j}(h_j)$. These inequalities can replace these functions
 397 in (9) with new variables $\zeta_{e,i}$, $\zeta_{p,j}$ and $\zeta_{l,j}$ respectively, thus transforming these equations into
 398 linear inequalities. Bound inequalities also arise on state variables q_i and h_j through Step 1.

The Linear Program will then have the following constraints:

$$h_{ext,i}^l \leq \zeta_{e,i} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_u} (B_{ij} h_j) \leq h_{ext,i}^u, \quad i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (12a)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} (B_{ij}^\top q_i) = \zeta_{p,j} + \zeta_{l,j}, \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u \quad (12b)$$

$$\lambda_{e,i}^l q_i + \beta_{e,i}^l \leq \zeta_{e,i} \leq \lambda_{e,i}^u q_i + \beta_{e,i}^u, \quad i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (12c)$$

$$\lambda_{p,j}^l h_j + \beta_{p,j}^l \leq \zeta_{p,j} \leq \lambda_{p,j}^u h_j + \beta_{p,j}^u, \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u. \quad (12d)$$

$$\lambda_{l,j}^l h_j + \beta_{l,j}^l \leq \zeta_{l,j} \leq \lambda_{l,j}^u h_j + \beta_{l,j}^u, \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u. \quad (12e)$$

$$q_i^l \leq q_i \leq q_i^u \quad i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (12f)$$

$$h_j^l \leq h_j \leq h_j^u \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_u \quad (12g)$$

400 Note that the interval parameters in (9a) are eliminated through the use of their upper
 401 and lower bounds to convert them into the inequalities (12a) and (12b). The LP decision
 402 variables vector is defined as $\bar{z} = [\bar{x}^\top, \bar{\zeta}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{(2n_l+3n_u)}$ where $\bar{x} = [\bar{q}^\top, \bar{h}^\top]^\top$ is the state
 403 vector and $\bar{\zeta} = [\bar{\zeta}_e^\top, \bar{\zeta}_l^\top, \bar{\zeta}_l^\top]^\top$ is the auxiliary variable vector. Using the constraints (12a) -
 404 (12g), two LP problems can be formulated for obtaining lower (LPmin) and upper (LPmax)
 405 bounds on each state z_i of the vector \bar{z} :

LPmin:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\{\bar{x}, \bar{\zeta}\}} \quad x_i \\ s.t. \quad (12a) - (12g) \end{array} \right\}$$

LPmax:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max_{\{\bar{x}, \bar{\zeta}\}} \quad x_i \\ s.t. \quad (12a) - (12g) \end{array} \right\}$$

Step 4: Solution of the linear interval system of equations

409 The objective of the optimization problem formulated in the previous section is to find
 410 the lower and upper bounds on the state vector \bar{x} that satisfy the inequalities (12a)-(12g). To
 411 achieve this, a total of $2(n_l + n_u)$ LPs must be solved where each problem will derive either
 412 the lower or upper bound of an individual state variable, indicated by x_i^* . This procedure is

413 described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Solution of LISE using LP

begin

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ **to** $n_l + n_u$ **do**
- 2: Minimize x_i by solving problem **LPmin**
- 3: $x_i^l = x_i^*$
- 4: Maximize x_i by solving problem **LPmax**
- 5: $x_i^u = x_i^*$
- 6: **end for**
- 7: $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = [\bar{x}^l, \bar{x}^u]$

return $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$

414 **Step 5: Iterative solution of the nonlinear interval system of equations**

415 In Algorithm 1 the linearized version of the original problem in (9) is solved. This is an
 416 outer interval solution to the nonlinear problem, which guarantees to include the interval hull
 417 solution. To find the smallest possible interval $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = [\bar{x}^l, \bar{x}^u]$ that satisfies (9), an iterative
 418 method is used. At each iteration m , the range $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}$ in which the optimization algorithm
 419 searches for an optimal solution becomes smaller and is redefined as $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(m+1)} = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(m)} \cap \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m+1)}$,
 420 where $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m+1)}$ are the bounds calculated for the state vector \bar{x} at iteration m . The iterations
 421 stop when the bounds on the state vector remain relatively unchanged, i.e. the change is
 422 smaller than a small number ϵ . The relative change in bounds is computed as follows:

423
$$e^{(m)} \triangleq \left| (\bar{x}^u^{(m)} - \bar{x}^l^{(m)}) - (\bar{x}^u^{(m-1)} - \bar{x}^l^{(m-1)}) \right|_1. \quad (13)$$

424 The overall procedure for the solution of the NISE is described in Algorithm 2. The resulting
 425 bounds are an OI solution of these equations that approximate closely the IH solution.

426 **CASE STUDIES**

427 In this section, the IHISE algorithm is applied on different WDN in order to demon-
 428 strate the calculated bounds and evaluate the performance of the algorithm. An illustrative
 429 example is given in the ‘‘Illustrative example’’ section, where the bounds on different states

Algorithm 2 Iterative solution of NISE

begin

- 1: Define initial bounds $\bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(0)}$ using physical properties.
 - 2: Calculate initial bounds $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}$ using the procedure in Step 1.
 - 3: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(0)} = \left[\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)\top} \bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(0)\top} \right]^\top$
 - 4: $m = 0$
 - 5: **while** $e^{(m)} > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 6: Bounding linearization of (9) for $\bar{x} \in \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(m)}$
 - 7: Formulate problems **LPmin** and **LPmax**
 - 8: Find $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m+1)}$ using **Algorithm 1**
 - 9: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(m+1)} = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{bnd}^{(m)} \cap \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m+1)}$
 - 10: $m = m + 1$;
 - 11: **end while**
- return**
- $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m)}$
-

430 are shown graphically and compared with bounds obtained by MCS. In the section “Re-
431 sults from benchmark networks” a more extensive analysis of the algorithm is presented,
432 as it is applied on different benchmark networks with varying characteristics. The perfor-
433 mance of the algorithm is evaluated by defining appropriate performance metrics and by
434 comparing the IHISE bounds with bounds obtained by MCS. In the simulations we assumed
435 a demand-driven modeling approach with no leakages, which translates into $f_{ext,j}(h_j) = 1$
436 and $\mathbf{q}_{leak,j}(h_j) = 0$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_u$ in Problem (9). This modelling approach allows us to evaluate
437 the performance of the algorithm using the established WDN simulation software EPANET
438 (Rossman 2000).

439 Illustrative example

440 The benchmark network “Net1” shown in Fig. 1 provided by EPANET, is used to
441 demonstrate the bounds on hydraulic states produced by the IHISE algorithm. The network
442 parameters are shown in Table 1. Realistic water demand patterns, are assigned at each
443 demand node.

444 The IHISE algorithm is used to generate bounds on water flows in pipes and hydraulic
445 heads at nodes of the network. The measurement uncertainty is defined as $\pm 5\%$ on the
446 given water demands at nodes, which is the typical error given by manufacturers of water

447 flow meters. Modeling uncertainty is also considered and it is defined as $\pm 5\%$ on pipe Hazen-
448 Williams coefficients. The simulation duration is 24 hours, with a discrete time step of one
449 hour.

450 Additionally, the same bounds are generated using Monte-Carlo Simulations (MCS) of the
451 network in EPANET. The demands are randomly varied at each simulation within a range
452 of $\pm 5\%$ of the given water demands at nodes. The uncertainty on pipe Hazen-Williams
453 coefficients is achieved by analogously varying pipe lengths, as the Hazen-Williams coeffi-
454 cients are linearly depended on this parameter. Uncertainty on pipe roughness coefficients
455 and pipe diameter can also be considered, but the effect on Hazen-Williams coefficient will
456 not be linear. The maximum and minimum value of each state is saved, defining the upper
457 and lower bounds. The number of simulations is set to 30 000. Note that MCS provide an
458 inner approximation of the bounds on each state and how close they are to the true bounds
459 depends on the number of simulations. Given the possible variations of the same network
460 for the given uncertainty, a sufficiently large number of simulations need to be performed
461 in order for the MCS to converge to the true bounds. Nevertheless, especially in small net-
462 works, the MCS bounds can be useful to evaluate the IHISE bounds, which are an outer
463 approximation of the true bounds, by: 1) verifying the correctness of the IHISE bounds by
464 checking if the MCS bounds are always a subset of the IHISE bounds and 2) evaluating the
465 conservativeness of the IHISE bounds by measuring their distance from the MCS bounds.

466 Simulation results for selected states which reflect the results for all the states are given
467 in Fig. 2. The IHISE bounds are compared with bounds generated using MCS for each state.
468 The figure illustrates that the MCS bounds are a subset of the IHISE bounds, while they
469 are also closely approximated. Note that, the true unknown bounds are enclosed between
470 the IHISE and MCS upper and lower bounds.

471 **Results from benchmark networks**

472 To evaluate the ability of IHISE to compute state bounds, five benchmark networks with
473 varying characteristics are used: “Anytown”, which was used as the basis for the original

474 “Battle of the Network Optimization Models” (Walski et al. 1987), “Net1”, “Net2” and
475 “Net3”, which are example networks in EPANET (Rossman 2000), and “ky3” from the
476 Kentucky Infrastructure Authority database of water distribution models (Jolly et al. 2014).
477 The networks and their characteristics are listed in Table 1.

478 The networks were carefully selected to have multiple varying characteristics in terms of
479 size, topology and types of elements they contain. Varying the network size, i.e. the number
480 of nodes and links, demonstrates the scalability of the IHISE algorithm by considering the
481 performance in networks with different number of *states*, i.e. heads at nodes and water flows
482 at links. Varying the number of reservoirs and tanks, as well as the number of pumps in the
483 network, reveals the ability of the algorithm to deal with these components. The topology of
484 the networks is also considered, specifically the complexity that arises in calculating hydraulic
485 states when the networks contain loops. This is quantified by calculating the *circuit rank*
486 of the network indicated by γ , which is then normalized by the number of links n_l of each
487 network. The resulting metric is defined as the *Loop Ratio*, given by $LR = \gamma/n_l$, $0 \leq LR <$
488 1 . A value of LR equal to zero means that there are no loops in the network, while LR
489 approaches the value of one in the case of a fully connected graph.

490 Note that the circuit rank of an undirected graph is defined as the number of independent
491 cycles, or the minimum number of edges that must be removed from the graph to break all
492 its cycles making it into a tree. It is calculated as $r = m - n + c$, where m is the number
493 of edges in the given graph, n is the number of vertices and c is the number of connected
494 components. The circuit rank is also known as the cyclomatic number and is used to indicate
495 the complexity of a program’s source code (McCabe 1976).

496 *Monte-Carlo and IHISE Simulations*

497 For each network, a random demand scenario is assigned which produces a feasible solu-
498 tion in EPANET, i.e. there are no negative pressures. Similar to the “Illustrative example”
499 section, the demand and modeling uncertainty is consider equal to $\pm 5\%$. The simulation
500 duration for all networks is 24 hours, with a discrete time step of one hour. The total number

501 of simulation steps is defined as $N_s = 24$.

502 MCS were performed for all networks using EPANET. The varying parameters are the
 503 nodal demands and pipe parameters, in the range defined by the assumed uncertainty. At
 504 each simulation, the minimum and maximum value of each state for each time step is saved,
 505 thus defining the lower and upper bounds on the state. Additionally, a robust estimate of the
 506 state under the considered uncertainties is calculated by taking all the simulated scenarios
 507 and calculating the mean value of each state at each time step. This is indicated by $q_{MC,i}^\mu(k)$
 508 for flow states and $h_{MC,j}^\mu(k)$ for head states and will be referred to as the *MCS state estimate*.

509 In order to perform an appropriate number of MCS and obtain quantifiable bounds for
 510 each network, a stopping criterion for the simulations is imposed, such that the change in
 511 all upper and lower flow-state and head-state bounds are less than $\Delta q(m^3/h)$ and $\Delta h(m)$
 512 respectively, for at least 5 000 consecutive simulations. The flows and heads in each network
 513 may belong in different value ranges, so Δq and Δh are calculated as a percentage of the
 514 absolute mean value of the MCS state estimates. The absolute mean value of flow-states
 515 and head-states respectively is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_q &= \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{k=1}^{N_s} \left(\frac{1}{n_l} \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} |q_{MC,i}^\mu(k)| \right) \\
 \mu_h &= \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{k=1}^{N_s} \left(\frac{1}{n_n} \sum_{j=1}^{n_n} |h_{MC,j}^\mu(k)| \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

517 The defined accuracies are then calculated as $\Delta q = 1\%(\mu_q)$ and $\Delta h = 1\%(\mu_h)$. Using this
 518 approach, it is assumed that the bound accuracy is given by Δq and Δh . Note that while
 519 this approach provides a degree of confidence for the accuracy of MCS bounds, it is not
 520 guaranteed that the deviation of these bounds from the actual bounds cannot be larger.

521 Using the IHISE algorithm, bounds for the state of all networks are computed, using
 522 the assumed uncertainty. As a technical note, due to the fact that the IHISE algorithm
 523 was designed from scratch without the use of other hydraulic solvers, the networks had to
 524 satisfy specific conditions in order for the current version of the algorithm to work and be

525 compared with the results from EPANET. The tank levels have to be measurable, so any
 526 tanks in the network model are replaced with variable head reservoirs. Control rules that
 527 open and close pumps depending on tank levels were removed from the model. Additionally,
 528 the head-loss formula should be set to Hazen-Williams. These limitations will be removed
 529 in future versions of the algorithm.

530 *Evaluation of bounds mean value*

531 An estimated value of the each state at each time step k is derived using the mean value
 532 of the IHISE bounds, which we will refer to as the *IHISE state estimate*. For flow-states
 533 this is calculated as $q_{IH,i}^\mu(k) = (q_{IH,i}^u(k) + q_{IH,i}^l(k)) / 2$, and for head-states this is calculated
 534 as $h_{IH,j}^\mu(k) = (h_{IH,j}^u(k) + h_{IH,j}^l(k)) / 2$. The IHISE state estimates are compared with the
 535 MCS state estimates, by calculating the Absolute Percentage Deviation (APD) of the IHISE
 536 state estimates to the MCS state estimates. Note that data from time steps where the MCS
 537 state estimate is close to zero are excluded from the evaluation, as they produced large
 538 percentages that are not representative of the results. The comparison shows that, for all
 539 networks, the Mean APD was less than 1%, while 99% of the time, the APD was less than
 540 8%. This indicates that, when no statistical characterization of the uncertainties is available,
 541 the mean value of the IHISE algorithm bounds can be used as a robust estimate of the system
 542 state.

543 *Evaluation of bounds*

544 For the evaluation of the IHISE algorithm bounds, we compare the lower bounds $x_{IH}^l =$
 545 $[q_{IH}^l \ h_{IH}^l]$ and upper bounds $x_{IH}^u = [q_{IH}^u \ h_{IH}^u]$ of the IHISE algorithm with the lower bounds
 546 $x_{MC}^l = [q_{MC}^l \ h_{MC}^l]$ and upper bounds $x_{MC}^u = [q_{MC}^u \ h_{MC}^u]$ derived from MCS respectively.
 547 First, the validity of the IHISE bounds was checked, i.e. $x_{IH,i}^l(k) < x_{MC,i}^l(k)$ and $x_{IH,i}^u(k) >$
 548 $x_{MC,i}^u(k)$ for all states i and all time steps k . The test indicated that there were no bound
 549 violations for networks “Net1”, “Net2” and “Anytown”. For “Net3”, bound violations occur
 550 for two flow-states, in time steps when the MCS flow estimate is less than $10^{-4}(m^3/h)$ and
 551 the MCS bound width is less than $10^{-2}(m^3/h)$. For “ky3”, bound violations occur in 1.77%

552 of the time, in specific states where the difference in width of the IHISE bounds and MCS
553 bounds is less than $0.4(m^3/h)$ for flows and less than $0.005(m)$ for heads. The violation
554 magnitude for any state and time step is less than 0.5% of the corresponding MCS state
555 estimate. All the observed bound violations occur in cases where the IHISE bounds are
556 very close to the MCS bounds. This can be explained by the fact that the IHISE algorithm
557 uses a completely independent hydraulic solver than EPANET, thus differences in solutions
558 may exist. Despite this fact, the differences in solutions made apparent by the violations
559 are insignificant and the validity test of the IHISE can be considered succesful if these are
560 attributed to modeling uncertainty which has not been taken into account.

561 Next, the Absolute Deviation (AD) of the two sets of bounds is evaluated separately for
562 flow-states and head-states, as they are measured in different units. The AD for flow-state
563 lower and upper bound is defined as $e_{q,i}^u(k) = q_{IH,i}^u(k) - q_{MC,i}^u(k)$ and $e_{q,i}^l(k) = q_{MC,i}^l(k) -$
564 $q_{IH,i}^l(k)$ respectively. Similarly, the AD for head-state lower and upper bounds is defined as
565 $e_{h,j}^l(k)$ and $e_{h,j}^u(k)$ respectively. An illustration of lower and upper bound ADs is shown in
566 Fig. 3. In Table 1 the mean AD for all states and time steps are shown for each network.
567 The results indicate mean errors for upper and lower bounds that are close to the accuracy
568 of MCS, ΔQ and Δh .

569 The area defined by the IHISE bounds is also an important evaluation metric. Since
570 the duration of simulations is the same for all states, evaluating the area is equivalent to
571 evaluating the width of the bounds. The width of the bounds for each time step is defined as
572 the difference between the upper and lower bound for each time step. For IHISE flow-state
573 bounds, for state i and time step k , the width is given by $w_{IH,i}^q(k) = q_{IH,i}^u(k) - q_{IH,i}^l(k)$.
574 Similarly, the width of IHISE head-state bounds, for state j and time step k , is defined as
575 $w_{IH,j}^h(k)$. The corresponding widths for MCS bounds are denoted by $w_{MC,i}^q(k)$ and $w_{MC,j}^h(k)$.
576 An illustration of bound widths is given in Fig. 3 In Table 1 the mean bound widths for
577 all states and time steps are shown for each network. The mean IHISE bound widths
578 is indicated by w_{IH}^q for flow-states and w_{IH}^h for heads-states, while the MCS bounds are

579 similarly indicated by w_{MC}^q and w_{MC}^h . As shown in Table 1, the difference between IHISE
 580 and MCS mean bound width for flow-states in different networks varies from $0.6(m^3/h)$ in
 581 “Net2” to $37.5(m^3/h)$ in “Net3”. Similarly, the mean bound width for head-states varies
 582 from $0.04(m)$ in “Net2” to $2.05(m)$ in “Net1”.

583 In order for the bounds width to give meaningful insight into the accuracy of the algo-
 584 rithm, they must be normalized relative to the absolute mean value of states for each network,
 585 i.e. μ_q for flow-states and μ_h for head-states. Using this normalization, the bound width can
 586 be viewed as a percentage of each state’s uncertainty. The *percent state uncertainty (PSU)*
 587 is calculated using the bound width-to-mean ratio as follows:

$$588 \eta_{alg}^s = \pm \frac{(w_{alg}^s/2)}{\mu_s} 100\%, \quad (15)$$

589 where $alg = \{IH, MC\}$ depending on the algorithm used, and $s = \{q, h\}$ depending on the
 590 type of state. This will allow the comparison between the calculated state uncertainty and
 591 the uncertainty on the network inputs, i.e. the demand and parameter uncertainty. It is
 592 recalled that the uncertainty on demands and parameters is defined as a percentage of their
 593 estimated value, which was set at $\pm 5\%$ in these simulations.

594 The average PSU for each network, indicated by $\eta_{alg}^s : alg = \{IH, MC\}, s = \{q, h\}$,
 595 is given in Table 1. For flow states, the PSU is, for both methods, close to the $\pm 5\%$
 596 input uncertainty which will be used as a reference point. Typically MCS have slightly less
 597 uncertainty and IHISE slightly more, with the exclusion of the looped network “Anytown”
 598 where both methods have more uncertainty, and the small network “Net1”, where both
 599 methods have more. For head-states, the results are much different, as both methods produce
 600 much less state uncertainty than the reference point, except in the case of “Net1” where the
 601 uncertainty is near $\pm 5\%$. The IHISE average PSU is at the worst case 2 times larger than
 602 the MCS average PSU. The worst cases present at the large network “ky3” but also in the
 603 highly looped network “Anytown”.

604 For additional insight, the maximum PSU for each network is calculated. This is calcu-
605 lated using the MCS state estimate for each state i and time step k as follows: $\max(\eta_{alg}^s) =$
606 $\max(w_{alg,i}^s(k)/s_i^\mu(k)) : alg = \{IH, MC\}, s = \{g, h\}$. Note that time steps when MCS state
607 estimates have values close to zero, were excluded from the evaluation as they produced
608 large percentages that are not representative of the results. As observed in Table 1, the
609 IHISE maximum PSU is at worst 3 times larger than the maximum PSU obtained by MCS.
610 However, the maximum values of PSU occur in only a few occasions. This is illustrated in
611 Appendix S3 of Supplemental Data, where the distribution of the PSU for IHISE and MCS
612 is plotted for network “ky3”.

613 The different operating scenarios of the networks resulting by the changing demands
614 may also affect the bounds of the IHISE algorithm. To evaluate this factor, the average
615 difference in PSU for all flow-states $\bar{\eta}_{IH}^q(k) - \bar{\eta}_{MC}^q(k)$ at each time step k is calculated. This
616 is then compared to the average nodal demand in the network $\bar{q}_{ext}(k)$ at each time step. By
617 performing correlation analysis, we obtain a correlation of 0.9483, 0.9995, 1.0000, 0.9273 and
618 0.9975 between these data, for the networks “Net1”, “Anytown”, “Net2”, “Net3” and “ky3”
619 respectively. In Appendix S4 of Supplemental Data, this correlation is illustrated by plotting
620 the average difference in PSU as a function of the average nodal demand for network “ky3”.
621 The average difference in PSU follows the pattern of average nodal demands. This can be
622 explained by the fact that the uncertainty on demands is proportional to the demand value,
623 as it was assumed in the design of the simulations, and MCS bounds become less accurate
624 when uncertainty in the network is larger, thus deviating more from the IHISE bounds.

625 *Simulation times*

626 The simulation *time* of either the IHISE algorithm or MCS for a single time step is
627 also evaluated, along with the average *iterations* needed by the IHISE algorithm to solve a
628 single time instance of the specific network and the number of MCS. The simulations were
629 performed on a personal computer with Intel Core i5-2400 CPU at 3.10GHz. Simulation
630 times of the IHISE algorithm are mainly depended on the size of the network, as observed in

631 Table 1. In Appendix S5 of Supplemental Data, an extrapolation of the simulation times for
632 the IHISE algorithm compared to the simulation times of MCS based on the five networks
633 of this case study is given. The estimated simulation time of the IHISE algorithm is always
634 less than the MCS time with the defined accuracy, while the time difference becomes larger
635 for larger networks.

636 The simulation time also depends on the complexity of the network, as it is evident in
637 Table 1 from the simulation time of the looped network “Anytown”. The IHISE algorithm
638 needs more iterations to converge to a solution for this network compared to the ”Net2”
639 which has similar number of states but is less looped. Similarly, more MCS are needed
640 for the looped network “Anytown” than ”Net2” for them to converge to a defined bound
641 accuracy.

642 **CONCLUSIONS**

643 In this work the problem of estimating bounds on WDN hydraulic states is addressed.
644 A new methodology is proposed that generates interval state estimates. The proposed *Iter-*
645 *ative Hydraulic Interval State Estimation* (IHISE) algorithm generates bounds on hydraulic
646 states of the network, by taking into account the water demand uncertainty and modeling
647 uncertainty in the form of uncertain pipe parameters. The uncertainties are modeled as
648 intervals. The results show that the proposed methodology is able to generate tight bounds
649 on hydraulic states and can be used in place of randomized methods such as Monte-Carlo
650 Simulations (MCS).

651 The advantage of this methodology over MCS is that the calculated bounds guarantee
652 the inclusion of the true system state, while the iterative nature of the algorithm makes
653 these bounds as tight as possible. An extension of this work is to use the generated bounds
654 for fault diagnosis methods that detect and localize leakages in the network. The proposed
655 methodology can be naturally used with model based fault-diagnosis and robust control
656 methodologies, because many of these rely on the availability of bounding state estimates
657 which are calculated by some knowledge of the system uncertainties. In the case of fault-

658 diagnosis, the bounding state estimates are used to create thresholds, which when violated
659 is an indication of a fault (Puig 2010). Additionally, the bounds on hydraulic states of
660 the network can be used to generate bounds on water quality states, since the dynamics of
661 hydraulic and quality states of a water network are interconnected.

662 A limitation of this methodology is that it does not model elements whose head function
663 is depended on pressure, such as pressure reduction valves. This is something that will be
664 considered in future work. Other elements that are used in WDN and are not modeled in this
665 work, are pressure control valves, flow control valves etc. Future work will model a variety
666 of additional components to be used with this methodology, and an interval hydraulic state
667 estimation toolkit will be released. Additionally, more extensive simulations on how this
668 methodology deals with pressure-driven demands and pressure-dependent leakages will be
669 provided.

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674 Cyprus, under the project SmartWater2020.

675 **SUPPLEMENTAL DATA**

676 A detailed description of the derivation of initial bounds on flow states, as described in
677 Step 1 of the IHISE algorithm in Section 3, is provided in Appendix S1. Appendix S2 contains
678 a detailed description of the bounding linearization procedure of Section 3, an illustrative
679 example showing the convergence over successive iterations and illustrative examples of the
680 application of this procedure on nonlinear functions of different hydraulic elements, pressure
681 dependent demand functions and leakage functions. Appendices S3–S5 provide additional
682 simulation data from the Case Study Section. Appendices S1–S5 are available online in the
683 ASCE Library (www.ascelibrary.org).

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815 **List of Tables**

816 1 Results of the IHISE algorithm on benchmark networks. 35

Networks:	Net1	Anytown	Net2	Net3	ky3
States	24	63	76	216	646
Loop Ratio	0.23	0.49	0.13	0.19	0.26
Junctions	9	19	35	92	269
Reservoirs	1	3	0	2	3
Tanks	1	0	1	3	3
Pipes	12	40	40	117	366
Pumps	1	1	0	2	5
Flow-states:					
μ_q (m^3/h)	551.98	75.93	13.33	469.02	42.12
Δq (m^3/h)	5.52	0.76	0.13	4.69	0.42
e_q^u (m^3/h)	5.77	6.49	0.32	19.01	1.60
e_q^l (m^3/h)	6.82	6.54	0.32	20.04	1.62
w_{MC}^q (m^3/h)	32.55	10.85	0.96	42.64	2.91
w_{IH}^q (m^3/h)	42.75	23.54	1.56	80.15	6.08
η_{MC}^q (%)	± 2.95	± 7.15	± 3.59	± 4.55	± 3.46
η_{IH}^q (%)	± 3.87	± 15.50	± 5.86	± 8.54	± 7.22
$\max(\eta_{MC}^q)$ (%)	± 19.33	± 78.62	± 23.12	± 95.71	± 62.53
$\max(\eta_{IH}^q)$ (%)	± 37.86	± 205.80	± 40.52	± 190.35	± 190.07
Head-states:					
μ_h (m)	63.06	42.92	43.69	52.89	48.04
Δh (m)	0.52	0.37	0.41	0.50	0.49
e_h^u (m)	1.34	0.06	0.02	0.74	0.08
e_h^l (m)	1.35	0.07	0.02	0.61	0.09
w_{MC}^h (m)	6.10	0.11	0.03	1.49	0.29
w_{IH}^h (m)	8.16	0.24	0.07	2.76	0.46
η_{MC}^h (%)	± 4.84	± 0.13	± 0.04	± 1.41	± 0.30
η_{IH}^h (%)	± 6.47	± 0.28	± 0.08	± 2.61	± 0.48
$\max(\eta_{MC}^h)$ (%)	± 12.99	± 0.29	± 0.10	± 1.82	± 1.71
$\max(\eta_{IH}^h)$ (%)	± 17.44	± 0.61	± 0.21	± 3.60	± 2.35
Times:					
MCS Number	5849	28993	21805	13977	32695
MCS (min)	1.71	3.84	4.36	11.74	34.49
IHISE (min)	0.01	0.12	0.08	0.96	13.72
IHISE Iterations	7.44	13.48	9.00	14.56	16.40

TABLE 1. Results of the IHISE algorithm on benchmark networks.

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Fig. 1. The benchmark network “Net1”, on which the IHISE algorithm is demonstrated.

Fig. 2. Comparison of selected pipes water flow bounds (above) and selected nodes hydraulic head bounds (below), generated by Monte-Carlo Simulations (blue solid area) and the IHISE algorithm (red dashed lines).

Fig. 3. Illustration of bound evaluation parameters.